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TACIT KNOWLEDGE IN INTERIOR ARCHITECTURE: INTERIOR ARCHITECTS ON THE DESIGNER - PAYING CLIENT - USER CLIENT RELATIONSHIP

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ABSTRACT

During the last decades, different authors have argued that interior architecture lacked a specific body of knowledge, especially in relationship to architecture (Abercrombie, 1990; Marshall-Baker, 2000; Clemons & Eckman, 2008). The article argues that this gap can be partially bridged by combining theoretical knowledge with insights into the actual design processes. In the actual process of designing interior spaces, some kind of knowledge production is involved (Heylighen et al., 2007), for which designers can rely on different knowledge types, such as 'explicit' and 'tacit' knowledge (Polanyi, 1967; Collins, 2010; Friedman, 2000). As the discipline of interior architecture is seeking a stronger body of theory (Marshall-Baker, 2000; Clemons & Eckman, 2008), it seems particularly interesting 'to bring tacit knowledge into articulate focus' (Friedman, 2000, p.13). Therefore, this paper aims to explore the concept of tacit knowledge and its particular value for interior architecture, and then, to present the results of in-depth interviews with interior architects, who have been involved in the process of designing commercial interiors.

Keywords: interior architecture, tacit knowledge, body of knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, theory of interior architecture has received increasing attention: it was argued that it lacked a specific body of knowledge, especially in relationship to architecture (Abercrombie, 1990; Marshall-Baker, 2000; Clemons & Eckman, 2008). At the same time however, academics in architecture noticed that existing

academic architectural knowledge hardly filtered down to practising architects (Neuckermans, 2004; Heylighen et al., 2007). Aiming to assure that academic knowledge can be transmitted to interior architectural practice, while in the meantime aiming to support the development of interior architecture's body of knowledge, Edwards (2011) pleads for combining the advancement of the discipline's theoretical knowledge base with insights into the actual design practices.

In the process of designing, some kind of knowledge production is involved (Heylighen et al., 2007), for which designers can rely on different knowledge types, such as 'explicit' and 'tacit' knowledge (Polanyi, 1967; Friedman, 2000). Solutions to design assignments never start with 'empty minds' (Zeisel, 2006). Instead, designers are influenced by their socio-cultural background and experiences from previous design projects. In other words, important knowledge in interior architectural practice is experience-based and tacit (Polanyi, 1967; Woo et al., 2004; Poldma & Thompson, 2009; Poldma, 2009, 2010; Collins, 2010). Next to this 'tacit knowledge' however, also 'explicit knowledge', i.e. codified knowledge that can be communicated through the use of formal language (Woo et al., 2004), influences the way one approaches new design assignments. As the discipline of interior architecture is seeking a stronger body of theory (Marshall-Baker, 2000; Clemons & Eckman, 2008), it seems particularly challenging 'to bring tacit knowledge into articulate focus' (Friedman, 2000, p.13), even more because 'tacit knowledge - the unspoken assumptions, interpretations, expectations, and conventions -

maybe more important to learn than explicit knowledge or skills' (Cuff, 1991, p.43).

So far, few authors (Woo et al., 2004; Heylighen et al., 2007) have focused on ways to gain access to and / or to share tacit knowledge in architectural or interior architectural practice. Therefore, this paper aims to explore the concept of tacit knowledge and to explain its particular value for interior architecture. Next, we will present the results of in-depth interviews with interior architects, who have been involved in the process of designing commercial interiors. Due to the accessibility and common presence of interiors, designed for commercial purposes, we take retail design as casus. Focusing our attention on studying retail stores allows to relatively easily study aspects typical for interior architecture, such as: close relationship to users, semiotics, light, choice of materials, etcetera.

TACIT KNOWLEDGE IN INTERIOR ARCHITECTURAL PRACTICE

When designing interior environments, designers rely on different types of knowledge, which are discussed in literature while using a variety of terms, among which 'practical knowledge', 'skills knowledge', 'tacit knowledge', 'implicit knowledge', 'experiential knowledge', 'codified knowledge' and 'explicit knowledge'. It is beyond the scope of this paper to discuss all of these terms; the authors would like to focus on 'tacit' and 'explicit knowledge', as these two types of knowledge tend to be paired in literature (Niederer, 2007; Poldma & Thompson, 2009).

In interior architectural practice, projects originate through the dynamic collaboration of designers with other parties, among which, what Zeisel (2006, p.50) calls, '*paying clients*' and '*user clients*'.

Figure 1. The user / needs gap (Zeisel, 1981 / 2006)

In Zeisel's (2006) terminology, 'paying clients' are those people who pay a designer for designing a particular interior space, which they were able to criticize during the design process. By 'user clients', Zeisel (2006) has in mind the people who eventually will 'use' the designed space. For designers, it is not easy to meet the needs and wants of this third party, as they mostly are not available to discuss the programme. Taking into account that design projects most often start with designers, working together with paying clients, concrete design teams often are composed of individuals from various backgrounds, all with various needs and wants and different levels of expertise. In many cases, concrete design projects originate from cross-disciplinary exchange and dialogue between the parties involved in the design process, whereby technical, codified or 'explicit' information is integrated with more intuitive, creative or 'tacit' information (Poldma & Thompson, 2009; Poldma, 2010). Indeed, interior architects design spaces after having investigated paying clients' - and if possible - user clients' needs and wants and after having studied and chosen materials, colors, lighting, furnishings, etcetera. In the end, the design of interior spaces originates when '*interior designers take a virtual idea and make it a living and active space, where intangible human endeavor comes together with physical lived experiences, aesthetic responses and functional contexts*' (Poldma, 2009, p.4663). Taking into account that interior architecture as a professional act integrates explicit and tacit forms of knowledge, Niederer (2007) and Poldma & Thompson (2009) plea for the inclusion of tacit knowledge within research. Also

Holm (2006) supports this vision, and cites Whiteley (1993, p.145), who already in 1993 indicated that *'tacit knowledge is acknowledged by many design methodologists to be an essential component of the skills and qualitative decision-making processes of designers'*. But what is tacit knowledge, and how can we get insight in this rather mystical concept?

Recently, Collins (2010) has done an effort to update Polanyi's (1967) conceptualization of tacit knowledge. Collins (2010) argues that in the postwar period wherein Polanyi lived, the world was dominated by science and *'the belief that logic, observation and experiment were, without question, the preeminent ways of obtaining sure knowledge'* (Collins, 2010, p.148). In Collins' viewpoint (2010), Polanyi thus was tempted to write on tacit knowledge as something rather mystical, an aura it somehow maintained. In an effort to change these perceptions concerning tacit and explicit forms of knowledge, Collins (2010) differentiates between three types of tacit knowledge (TK): 'relational' (RTK), 'somatic' (STK) and 'collective' (CTK). RTK is tacit because of contingencies that have to do with relations between people, history, tradition and logistics. For instance, sometimes knowledge that in theory could be told among different partners is deliberately kept hidden (in Collins' (2010) terminology, this concerns so-called 'concealed knowledge'). STK has to do with the nature and possibilities of the human body and brain, whereas CTK concerns knowledge that one can acquire only by being embedded in society. Collins (2010) is convinced that these three types are necessary vehicles to gain competence in a particular discipline. Furthermore, Collins (2010) states that questions about the nature of tacit knowledge are often linked to questions about the transferability of tacit knowledge. How can it be studied? And can or should it be possible to convert different types of tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge?

A common feature in the existing studies on interior architecture, is a focus on the causal relationship between people and their environment. Until yet, when researchers study the design of an interior space, they often focus on causal relationships between people and their environment. In this form of design inquiry, researchers formulate a priori hypotheses, aiming to demonstrate how evidence-

based knowledge of the man-environment relationship can inform the design process. According to Poldma (2009, 2010), this type of research often is positivist inspired, aiming to seek 'objective knowledge'. A limitation of this approach however is that it does not take into account subjective issues such as meanings people attach to certain aspects or occurrences that take place in the design process. However, these meanings and subjective insights are part of tacit forms of knowledge (Poldma, 2010). So far, tacit knowledge is usually associated with practical knowledge and skill, as opposed to the concept of 'empirical research' (Holm, 2006; Niedderer, 2007). It is also regarded as excluded from academic research, *'because it withstands articulation and argumentation and thus wider dissemination'* (Niedderer, 2007, p.6). However, Niedderer (2007) is convinced that the inclusion of tacit knowledge in academic research is necessary, firstly because it would allow tacit knowledge to be brought into the actual research process. Secondly, bringing tacit knowledge in academic research could also trigger architects' and interior architects' attention for research and lift the stigma on more positivist inspired inquiry modes (Holm, 2006; Poldma, 2009). Poldma & Thompson (2009) argue that this entails doing research in ways that allow the researcher to access tacit knowledge in interior architectural practice. In their opinion, designed interior space should be studied as the *'dynamic backdrop of human activity'* (Poldma & Thompson, 2009, p.4668), whereby attention should be given to conversations, perceptions and experiences of the stakeholders involved in the design process, which inevitable have subjective and tacit characteristics (Nelson & Stolterman, 2003). Poldma & Thompson (2009) furthermore argue that known empirical methods of tacit knowledge production in research can be used to achieve this goal. One of the knowledge elicitation techniques which can be applied to gain access to tacit forms of knowledge, is interviewing (Garcia-Perez & Mitra, 2007; Cross, 2011). Cross (2011, p.8) states that *'asking designers about what they do is perhaps the simplest and most direct form of inquiry into design ability, although this technique has not in fact been practiced extensively'*. By actually talking to designers, the authors aim to try to reveal designers' 'locked in' or

‘tacit’ knowledge on different kinds of aspects they need to take into account in the process of designing interior spaces.

REVEALING TACIT KNOWLEDGE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: ETHNOGRAPHIC INTERVIEWS

Ethnographic interviews (Spradley, 1979) are also known in literature as ‘in-depth’ or ‘unstructured interviews’ (Legard, Keegan & Ward, 2003). A basic research objective for employing these kinds of interviews is to gain in-depth insight in the interviewees’ ideas and reflections on the steps they undertake generally, or when developing particular works of design (Cross, 2006). Ethnographic interviews involve asking relatively open-ended questions, aiming to enable the researcher to learn about and understand the interviewees’ ideas on the topic of interest (Spradley, 1979). When studying relatively new domains, employing this type of interview method can be particularly useful. As Firmin (2008) states, *‘in such circumstances, it is not reasonable to ask a set of pre-established questions of the participant. Rather, researchers approach the interviews more inductively’* (p.907). Ethnographic interviews may also be helpful when a project’s principal goal is depth, rather than breadth (Firmin, 2008). These arguments seem well matched with our goals: to achieve a better understanding of the practice of designing commercial interiors, by digging into the significance of different actions and choices the involved designers had to take in the design process.

ETHNOGRAPHIC INTERVIEWS: RESEARCH DESIGN AND DATA ANALYSES

In the first months of 2010, different designers were contacted in our search for what Morse (1998) calls ‘good informants’ (p.73). According to Morse (1998), good informants are those people who have the knowledge and experience the researcher requires, have the ability to reflect on the central research topic, are communicative, have time and are willing to participate in the research project. Our search for ‘good informants’ resulted in the set-up of interviews with six retail and interior designers, who had been involved in the design process of a commercial interior.

All interviews took place at the designers’ offices, which can be considered as the interviewees’ ‘natural settings’. In line with what knowledgeable qualitative researchers recommend (Fontana & Frey, 2000; Legard et al., 2003), we prepared a list of key topics for the interview in advance. In the interview, the authors aimed to understand the interviewees’ perspectives on and ideas about different kinds of aspects they need to take into account in the process of designing commercial interiors. The interviews started by asking about the concept of a particular store and continued with specific questions on one case. After some time, inspired by Zeisel’s model of the designer / paying client / user client relationship (2006), we shifted to more abstract questions on these issues. We asked retailers and designers about their viewpoints on the relationships between the parties, involved in the process of designing and letting function a commercial interior. We also prepared questions on how the relationship between a certain designer and a paying client originated, but more often than not, the interviewer did not need to follow the topic list, as the interviewees started out discussing these aspects spontaneously in the flow of the interview. During the interview, the interaction between the researcher and interviewee sometimes resulted in the interviewee asking the researcher a question, which illustrates the open-ended character of the interview process. When we noted that the same specific patterns of thought emerged over and over again in the process of interviewing our informants, we decided that it was time *‘to leave the field’* (Fetterman, 1997, p.10) and to start analyzing the collected data.

The interviews lasted between one and two hours, were audio-taped and transcribed verbatim in their whole. All interviews were processed with ATLAS.ti version WIN 5.0 (Scientific Software Development, n.d.). Such a computer-aided data analysis package not only can reduce analysis time and permits flexibility while analyzing data, but it also forces the involved researchers to make procedures more systematic and explicit. As such, computer-aided methods can help to enhance the validity and reliability of research findings from qualitative studies (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Kelle & Laurie, 1995). Initial reading and re-reading of the interview

transcripts was followed by assigning codes in ATLAS.ti to specific words or to sections of text, used by the interviewees. The designer - paying client (i.c. retailer) - user client (i.c. consumer) model developed by Zeisel (2006) functioned as a guide to help us assigning codes in ATLAS.ti. Codes were assigned each time an interviewee discussed one of these aspects. While re-reading the interview transcripts multiple times, additional coding was performed, as other themes emerged in the interview data. The software helped us to study data, held within each code. In that way, the interview data offered an insight in how relationships between designer and paying clients originate and evolve in the design process, how these stakeholders collaborate to work out design concepts and how designers and paying clients try to judge what user clients of commercial interiors today (and in the near future) seem to need and value in commercial settings.

ETHNOGRAPHIC INTERVIEWS: RESEARCH RESULTS

Inspired by Zeisel's model (2006) we discovered the following themes in the interview data: (1) origin of decision to design or to reverse an existing design of an interior space (2) creation of designer - paying client relationship (3) development of a retail design store concept (4) delivering a store concept and the 'after life' of a store concept. In what follows, each of these themes is discussed on the basis of the interview data. Selected typical verbatim quotations (translated from Dutch to English) are added for the sake of argumentation and illustration (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Fetterman, 1997).

Decision to design or reverse an existing design of an interior space

The decision to design a new commercial interior, whether it concerns a completely new project or the reversion of an already existing store design, lies in the hands of the 'paying client' (i.e. the retailer). As figure 2 indicates, this decision can be made either autonomously by the paying client, or by the paying client after having noticed and / or discussed changing needs and wants with his target audience, i.e. his 'user clients'.

Figure 2. Stakeholders involved in decision to design or reverse interior architecture.

When discussing the issue of reversibility of retail design, the interviewees' viewpoints differed. Most designers were convinced that newly designed interior spaces can last for a relatively long period of time (one designer for instance talked about ten years), whereas another designer was convinced that retail stores should alter the design of their interiors every two years. According to his opinion, this could be done by relatively small design alterations, but nevertheless, every four years at least a large reversion seemed necessary. However, most designers indicated that reversing the design of a retail store implies considerable investments, which makes it almost impossible to transform the interior on a rapidly repeating basis. This certainly seems to be the case for small scale retailers. Apart from this economic argument, one designer also indicated in the course of the interview that he was convinced that a strong concept for retail design can survive for a relatively long period of time. In the interview, he agreed that this viewpoint could be '*different from currently pretty standard viewpoints of big box retailers concerning this topic*'. Issues such as reversibility of retail design or the lifespan of a retail store's design are examples of topics which are not rapidly discussed by retail designers and interior architects. This is understandable, as freely talking about such issues actually reveals at least some part of a design studio's design philosophy. Our sample of interviewees already illustrated that some designers are proponents of relatively long lasting, strong store concepts, whether other interviewees seem to work according to the market principles of big box

retailers, who generally decide to alter the retail design of their stores far more quickly than smaller scale retailers. The discussion of this topic during the interviewing can thus be considered as an example of relational tacit knowledge (i.e. concealed knowledge) and somatic tacit knowledge that we were able to reveal.

Creation of designer - paying client relationship

When the decision to alter the design of a retail store has been taken, the paying client has two possibilities: he can choose to alter the design completely by himself, under his own responsibility. Or he can opt to contact a professional, i.e. a designer with the degree of expertise and experience the paying client is looking for (see figure 3).

Figure 3. Stakeholders involved in creation of designer - paying client relationship.

During the interviews, most designers indicated that paying clients particularly chose for their design studio for obvious reasons, such as reputation. One designer said that ‘when they came to us, we already had references to retail related projects we performed in the past. We had been able to publish on these design projects in retail related magazines, which seem to be well-known in the retail sector’. Another designer said paying clients often choose to cooperate with a particular design studio while primordially basing oneself on professional networking: a retailer for instance ‘knows’ a particular designer, and can decide to work with this ‘known’ design studio as a kind of friendly gesture between professional colleagues. Interviewees for instance confirmed that sometimes they already had a very good contact with

a particular retailer, which helped them in getting the design assignment being allocated to their design studio. Also informal networking can help in drawing in new design assignments, as another designer confirmed in the course of the interview: ‘the paying client had a cousin, who is a practicing architect in Ghent. His studio however was too far away from the new location for the clients’ retail store, so he passed on our name. Soon afterwards, we had a first conversation with the client in question, and the next day, we already visited the new location together’. Talking about these kinds of issues again seems not to be very common among interior architects and retail designers, as no one is eager to get adversaries informed on how particular design assignments are being allocated to particular design studios.

Development of a retail design store concept

The next step in the design process of a commercial interior is the development of the retail store concept. Retail concepts are worked out in collaboration between paying clients and designers, whereby they most of the time will aim to address the needs and wants of the paying client’s target group of user clients.

Figure 4. Stakeholders involved in development of retail design store concept

In the course of the interview, most of the interviewees indicated that they generally develop a particular concept nowadays by working around a

particular theme or story. Working with themes or stories is an interesting starting-point for the development of a store concept, as it first of all allows to clearly discuss (and eventually try to sell) the store concept with the paying client. Secondly, it also helps to bring a clear story to the user clients. When developing the store concept, the collaboration between paying client and designer usually will aim to bring together the retail design and the retail branding of the commercial interior. One interviewee for instance stated that *'a retail brand most of the time embodies a certain lifestyle, and this needs to be reflected in the design of the store environment. People have to be able to be absorbed in the world of the brand'*. Another interviewee indicated that the choice for certain colors and materials needs to fit with the retail brand's image. Sometimes, the 'look and feel' one chooses for the design of a commercial interior is passed through to the communication of the retail brand. Hence, the choice for a particular retail design can trigger improvements of the communication of the retail brand. In the course of the interview, designers also pointed to initiatives they took to being able to address the needs and wants of the paying client's target group of user clients. One designer for instance said that his design studio tried to take current trends into account when developing new store concepts. Taken into account that a lot of people currently are living busy lives, characterized by time pressure and stress, his studio currently was trying to *'create totally different worlds into which people could escape from day-to-day worries'* in their design works-in-progress. Evidently, budgetary and where applicable, legislative considerations also play a major role in developing store concepts. Different interviewees indicated that sometimes not all aspects a designer thinks about or wants to implement in a store concept can be preserved in the final draft of the concept.

By talking about this issue, the interviewed designers offered us insight in their way to approach the development of new concepts. Again, these kinds of topics normally belong to the internal affairs of a design studio. In other words, by allowing us to talk about this topic, the sample of designers we were

able to interview revealed a part of their studio's 'concealed knowledge', which is one of the forms of relational tacit knowledge which Collins (2010) describes.

Delivering a store concept and the 'after life' of a store concept

The design process of an interior and retail design agency concludes with the designer or the design team delivering a store concept to the paying client. In this step of the design process, the concept still can be altered by the paying client.

Figure 5. Stakeholders involved in decision to deliver a store concept and the 'after life' of a store concept

While discussing this step in the design process, different interviewees pointed to the alterations paying clients sometimes make to the store concepts in the form the designers deliver them to the paying client. One interviewee for instance said *'we were not able to decide where the airconditioning should be placed. He already was placed on an awkward spot, and at the time of the design reversion, the paying client had no budget left to re-locate the airconditioning. So, the retail design as it currently is still has some aspects with which we are not really pleased, but there is nothing we can do about that'*. Another interviewee admitted it is not always easy to convince paying clients to potentially give up some square meters of the retail space to literally leave some space open for what she called *'creative initiatives'*, such as for instance leaving open a

segment of the interior for storytelling to future user clients. In the course of the interview, this designer also said: *'in the end, a paying client evidently always wants to sell as much as possible. From their point of view, this is a very logical argument, as they most often also need to pay a lot of rent for their retail spaces'*.

Most of the time, the job of design studios stops with the concrete execution of a particular retail store concept by building contractors (Mesher, 2010). What happens afterwards to the concretely designed environment is out of the designer's responsibilities. Sometimes, the interviewees acknowledged they not always appreciate what happened to their designed concepts after execution of the concept in retail practice. One interviewee for instance stated that he recently heard that a new department was added to one of the retail stores for which he developed the store concept. However, he was not eager to go and watch how this department was added to the existing retail environment, as he had not been involved in this new process. Also other interviewees admitted that they did not know if the retail stores for which they had developed the store concepts still looked the way they did after they had developed the store concept. As a designer said, *'we as designers, we deliver the framework wherein our client (i.e. the paying client) is free to start merchandising. We do not say to our client that they should place a particular object on a certain spot. That is a merchandiser's job'*. Next to paying clients, who evidently play a key role in deciding on the 'after life' of a retail store concept, also user clients can influence the way a store concept lives further after having been implemented. It is only by observing how user clients function in a designed space and by actually talking to them that paying clients can learn more on the question how the newly designed space is being experienced by its visitors. This can inform paying clients on how the new design is being perceived by its user clients. During the interviews we had, every designer freely discussed the topics of delivering a store concept and the 'after life' of their concepts. To the authors' knowledge, until yet, very few academic literature has focused on revealing these types of tacit knowledge from designers. However, to our

viewpoint, it seems particularly interesting to enable designers to contribute in this way to the scientific development of their professional discipline.

CONCLUSION

Taking into account that in concrete design processes, interior architects and retail designers combine explicit and tacit forms of knowledge, secondly, that more explicit forms of knowledge in (interior) architectural practice already have been widely documented, and thirdly, that focusing on tacit knowledge is interesting as it seems to be a way to involve design practitioners in the process of contributing to the scientific development of the discipline, it seemed particularly interesting to focus our attention in this paper on revealing different types of tacit knowledge of interior architects and retail designers. Therefore, this paper aimed to firstly explore the concept of tacit knowledge and its particular value for interior architecture, and secondly, to present the results of in-depth interviews with interior architects, who have been involved in the process of designing commercial interiors. Inspired by Zeisel's (2006) model concerning the designer / paying client / user client relationship, analyses on the interview data revealed tacit knowledge from the interviewed designers concerning different themes: (1) the origin of the decision to design a new or to revise an already existing commercial interior (2) the creation of the designer - paying client relationship (3) the development of a store concept (4) the final step in the design process, i.e. the delivering of the store concept and designers' viewpoints on what we have called the 'after life' of a store concept. In the course of the interviews, while being very 'open' to us concerning these topics, our interviewees in fact allowed us to take a look behind the scenes of actual design practices in their respective design studios. By allowing us to gain insight in different types of their 'tacit' or 'locked in' knowledge, the interviewed designers helped to contribute to the scientific development of the body of knowledge of interior architecture in general, and retail design in particular. In the course of the interviews, mostly 'relational' (RTK) and sometimes 'somatic' (STK) tacit knowledge was revealed. 'Somatic tacit knowledge' (STK), and certainly 'collective tacit

knowledge' (CTK) are difficult types of tacit knowledge to gain access to. Our research findings thus support what Collins (2010, p. 138) described, namely that '...the deep mystery remains how to make explicable the way that individuals acquire collective tacit knowledge at all. We can describe the circumstances under which it is acquired, but we cannot describe or explain the mechanism nor build machines that can mimic it'.

By having applied this research approach, we hope to have attracted the attention of our design peers to continue to help contribute to academic research in interior architecture in the future.

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